

HARMONY OF ECONOMIC REFORM AND SPIRITUAL LIFE

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Annotation: the article analyzes some views related to economic reforms and its impact on the spiritual image of the individual. The process of implementing economic reforms and its impact on spiritual life have been studied.

Key words: economy, globalization, value, society, spirituality, personality spirituality, spiritual maturity, integration, financial culture.

Our people gained independence and determined their own path of rebirth. In our country, along with the economy, fundamental reforms are carried out in socio-spiritual life. Spirituality was recognized as a legal democratic, like economics, an important factor in the construction of civil society, one of the priorities of Public Policy. One of the main goals pursued by spiritual reforms is to educate a spiritually mature individual. Spiritual maturity is the ability of a person to adapt his personal interests to the interests of the community, el-ulus, the land. This requires a person to correctly understand both his own interests and the interests of society, not to fly to false values, attractive, but puch and mercenary calls, not to be deceived. The main goal of the socio-spiritual reforms being carried out is to revive the national cultural values and heritage of ancestors, to convey their original content to the future avlo, to form a harmonious generation on the principles of humanism, tolerance. Achieving such goals is not self-fulfilling. This requires, in addition to spirituality, great economic opportunities. The fulfillment of the Indigenous interests of the people of Uzbekistan, high aspirations, noble intentions and great deeds is especially dependent on the younger generation of our entire people. With this in

mind, the head of state stressed: "it is important to attract our talented and educated youth to entrepreneurship widely," he said.

The relationship of economy and spirituality is a very colorful and complex process that requires interaction, and one always assumes the other. The economy creates material conditions for the development of spirituality. "The needs, demands of the economy serve as a " customer " in relation to spirituality. For example, the creation of new technologies, the improvement of Labor weapons and the like serve to develop science, technical creativity. To the complication of the production process, an increase in the level of knowledge assumes the formation of new labor skills in workers and specialists, their qualifications are constantly growing. This affects the development of the system of training, retraining, education and education in general in society, changes in the spiritual and psychological environment, increased predisposition to rationalization, ingenuity, technical creativity in production and marriage. In addition, the extensibility of communicating various goods, products and types of services to buyers has given rise to various exhibitions, shows, concourses, lotteries and, finally, the advertising and Information Industry.

In turn, the growth of spirituality; scientific and technological discoveries, an increase in the knowledge and skills of the population, a change in economic thinking, the pursuit of high social milestones, the pursuit of innovations develop the economy. It is impossible to create a humane society only by developing the economy and technology. Because only when we are concerned about the economy and technology will the likelihood of finding a decision increase that a technocratic society will lose its identity and turn a person into a simple bolt of the economy.

Just economic growth, as noted above, does not bring prosperity to the life of a person and society. The rational use of resources is also required to have a financial culture when determining the unity of needs and opportunities. Financial culture is a concept that expresses the unity of the financial consciousness and activity of a

person. It is composed, on the one hand, on the basis of the financial awareness, knowledge and imagination of the individual, on the other, on the norms and models of his financial activity, and on the third, on the basis of financial purpose-provisions, values.

In conditions where financial culture is low, no economic opportunity leads to a spiritual upsurge. It should be noted that financial culture ensures successful socialization and adaptation of a person to society, allows you to get up from social cocoons, sets the stage for the rapid development of a professional career, the development of one's own personality, the acquisition of self-development peaks. The social importance of an individual having a high financial culture is also great: as the financial culture of individuals rises, financial relations in society also improve, the quality of financial services increases.

Many areas of spirituality will not develop if economic growth does not occur, the people's living well-being does not rise: ideological education, art, media, printing, the material base of science will be disadvantaged, the creative search of society will subside. Opportunities arise for the spread of ideological intolerance, fanaticism in various forms. This, in turn, creates additional difficulties for the development of the economy, since the needs of the economy for new technologies, new ideas are not adequately met. Economic thinking begins to lag behind the demand of the period. Where humanity, honesty is not sufficiently taken into account, there is a confrontation between the employer and the recruiter, and not a social partnership. In other words, spirituality affects the rhinoceros of the economy, its degree of creakiness or inertia, the degree of openness to innovation and renewal. The meiori - evaluative nature of spirituality encourages the economy to fulfill burnt demands on its agenda or to neglect society in relation to them.

The conclusion is that it is possible to prevent and eliminate any threats and harassment by the formation of genuine knowledge, consistent and continuous implementation of the process of spiritual education. And for this, it is important that

each member of our society has a clear idea of what reform and change is aimed at, how it is carried out and its outcome, and organizes its activities on this basis. The strong faith in the hearts of our people, the infinite sense of gratitude in their language, the main reason for the gratitude mood, the folkiness of the reforms being carried out, all of them are in service with the human factor, its interests. In the process, spirituality gives a person strength, motivates him to act and becomes his solid trust.

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